

ENDOTHELIAL DYSFUNCTION AND PLACENTAL INSUFFICIENCY IN OBESITY-RELATED PREECLAMPSIA

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Background. *Maternal obesity is a significant risk factor for preeclampsia and is associated with increased maternal and perinatal morbidity. Metabolic disturbances, including chronic inflammation, oxidative stress, and insulin resistance, contribute to vascular dysfunction during pregnancy. However, the clinical relationship between endothelial dysfunction and placental insufficiency in obese pregnant women remains insufficiently characterized. This highlights the importance of early identification of vascular dysfunction in high-risk pregnancies.*

Keywords: *preeclampsia, maternal obesity, endothelial dysfunction, placental insufficiency, Doppler ultrasonography.*

Objective. To evaluate the relationship between endothelial dysfunction and placental insufficiency in obesity-related preeclampsia.

Materials and Methods. A prospective observational study was conducted at the regional perinatal center maternity hospital over 6 months and included 68 pregnant women at 28–36 weeks of gestation. The main group consisted of 38 women with obesity-associated preeclampsia, while the control group included 30 women with normal pregnancy and body mass index. Inclusion criteria were age 18–40 years, singleton pregnancy, gestational age 28–36 weeks, and confirmed preeclampsia with obesity (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²). Exclusion criteria included multiple pregnancy, chronic hypertension, diabetes mellitus, renal, cardiovascular or autoimmune diseases, and infectious conditions. Endothelial function was assessed by serum nitric oxide (NO) and endothelin-1 (ET-1) levels, while placental insufficiency was evaluated using Doppler ultrasonography (uterine artery RI and umbilical artery S/D ratio). Statistical analysis was performed using Student's t-test and Pearson correlation coefficient, with $p < 0.05$ considered statistically significant.

Results. Impaired uteroplacental blood flow was observed in 71.1% of women in the study group, compared to 16.7% in the control group ($p < 0.01$). Mean nitric oxide levels were reduced by 32.4%, whereas endothelin-1 levels increased by 1.7 times in women with obesity-related preeclampsia. Signs of endothelial dysfunction were identified in 73.7% of cases. A statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.64$, $p < 0.01$) was found between Doppler indicators of placental insufficiency and markers of endothelial dysfunction. In addition, elevated inflammatory markers suggested a contribution of metabolic imbalance to disease progression. These findings confirm the significant role of endothelial dysfunction in the pathogenesis of placental insufficiency.

Conclusion. Endothelial dysfunction and placental insufficiency are closely interconnected processes in obesity-related preeclampsia, observed in more than 70% of cases. Their interaction forms a self-perpetuating pathogenic cycle that contributes to disease severity. Early detection of

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endothelial dysfunction may improve clinical outcomes through timely prevention and management strategies.

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